

Adaptation of SVM for novelty detection in long-term diagnostic data with Gaussian and non-Gaussian disturbance

Forough Moosavi ¹

¹ Faculty of Geoen지니어ing, Mining and Geology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Na Grobli 15, 50-421 Wrocław, Poland; forougholsadat.moosavi@pwr.edu.pl (F.M.); hamid.shiri@pwr.edu.pl (H.S.); jacek.wodecki@pwr.edu.pl (J.W.)

² Faculty of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Hugo Steinhaus Center, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wyspińskiego 27, 50-370 Wrocław, Poland; agnieszka.wylomska@pwr.edu.pl

* Correspondence: radoslaw.zimroz@pwr.edu.pl

Abstract: Machine diagnostics is simply finding the difference between healthy and faulty components. To do this we need threshold value. In the case of the unique machine, we do not have a bad condition example. Then we use so-called Novelty Detection. In the paper, we propose Support Vector Machine (SVM) for novelty detection applied to Health Index data. We applied the moving window approach and simple statistical parametrisation of data inside the window. We build the model in multidimensional (mD) space. The estimated hypersphere is a border describing shape of the mD model. Then we proposed an extension of the procedure - if data is inside the border, we can use it to re-training the model. If data are outside the border - this is a novelty. Basically, it means we do not know these data, and it cannot be recognised as a healthy case; thus, it is faulty. We defined the size of the mD hypersphere (for $m=2$), describing the location of the good-condition data cloud as a potential feature. If the size of the data cloud is growing, it means more dispersion of the data. We showed the efficiency of the method using simulations and two well-known real data sets. It is essential to consider Gaussian and non-Gaussian data sets.

Keywords: long-term, diagnostic, data modelling, threshold setting, novelty detection, One class classification, statistical analysis, heavy-tailed distribution, machine learning.

Citation: Moosavi, F.; Shiri, H.; Wodecki, J.; Wyłomańska, A.; Zimroz, R. Adaptation of SVM for novelty detection in long-term diagnostic data with Gaussian and non-Gaussian disturbance. *Journal Not Specified* **2021**, *1*, 0. <https://doi.org/>

Received:
Accepted:
Published:

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted to *Journal Not Specified* for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Condition Monitoring systems have become more and more popular in the industry. They are used to acquire some informative signals, process them to extract the features describing the machine condition, and compare values of features with established limit values (thresholds) related to the transition from good condition to slow degradation (Warning) and finally to rapid degradation (Alarm). A key issue is to establish these limited values in practical situations. In some cases, these values are provided by manufacturers. Unfortunately, it should be discovered by experts or advanced data-driven methods in most cases, particularly for unique machines in the mining industry.

One class classification (OCC) is a concept that uses machine learning methods when the data training set is related to one class, mostly a "healthy" condition. Then, a trained system is used to detect anomalous data points. In recent years OCC has been used frequently for outlier detection [1–4] and novelty detection [5–9]. For instance, Bartkowiak et al. [1] used OCC for outlier analysis of nonstationary signals of the gearbox. Riccardo La Grassa et al. [9] developed one class minimum spanning tree by employing a convolution neural network for novelty detection. Wang Xiaoyou et al. [10] used unsupervised one-class classification for the assessment of structural health monitoring of the bridge. Also, it should be noted that the outlier and novelty detection differ in concept and application. In outlier detection, the training data set may be composed of normal and anomaly data. The responsibility is to define a boundary between these two classes and apply this boundary to the test data set, which may

37 include both normal and anomalous data. However, in novelty detection, the training
 38 data set dose not containe anomaly data, and the anomaly data appear in the test data
 39 sets [11]. In general, the classifier's model could be categorized into three leading groups:
 40 density-based, reconstruction-based, and boundary-based.

41 Density-based one-class classification approach is developed based on estimating
 42 the training data density and comparing it with a threshold. This family of OCC has the
 43 most efficiency when a high sample of training data is available. The Gaussian method
 44 and the mixture of Gaussians are known as density-based methods. The boundary-
 45 based method tries optimizing the boundary as a modeling challenge to find a closed
 46 boundary around the training data. Any sample located outside this boundary is known
 47 as an outlier or anomaly. Compared to the density-based approach, the boundary-
 48 based method needs fewer data samples to achieve the same performance. One of the
 49 popular boundary-based methods is the one-class support vector machine (OCC-SVM)
 50 which is used regularly in the literature. The reconstruction-based method is developed
 51 based on prior knowledge about a particular domain of historical data to generate a
 52 model. Outlier samples would generally not concede with the historical data assumption
 53 embedded in the models, and therefore, any sample with a high reconstruction error
 54 is assumed to be an outlier. This approach represents an input pattern as an output
 55 and tries to minimize the reconstruction error. Principal component analysis (PCA) [12],
 56 multi-layer perceptron (MLP) [13], and K-means clustering-based one-class classifier
 57 [14], are reconstruction-based models.

58 The paper proposes an application of the SVM-based one-class classification ap-
 59 proach. Next, some procedure adaptation is delivered to include new data in the training
 60 process. A new feature for decision-making based on OCC-SVM is proposed as the final
 61 result.

62 1.1. Lifetime curve model

63 The lifetime curve shape follows the model known in the literature [15,16]. It
 64 consists of 3 regimes: healthy condition, slow degradation (degradation stage), and
 65 rapid degradation (critical stage). The data could be modeled as a mixture of trend
 66 and random components. The random component usually is Gaussian noise see Fig.
 67 1; however, in some cases, the raw data definitely contain random components with
 68 non-Gaussian distribution, see Fig. 4.

Figure 1. Long-term data variation model used in this paper - Gaussian case [15]

69 2. Methodology

70 2.1. Lifetime curve statistical parametrization

71 say something about other HIs

72

73 equations for these statistics

74

75 2.1.1. Statistic features

76 The raw features obtained from the monitored system can be described in a multi-
 77 dimensional way by descriptive statistics. Such a representation allows the highlighting
 78 of some properties of data. Several statistical parameters are calculated using a moving
 79 window to preselect a small portion of data for each segment. As a result, one may
 80 obtain a data segmentation matrix (DSM) with dimension N segments \times M features, see
 81 Fig. 2

Figure 2. Long-term data variation parametrization used in this paper

82 2.2. OCC using SVM

83 As discussed in the introduction, OCC-SVM is one of the well-known and influen-
 84 tial OCC techniques developed to address the OCC problem in the literature. In this
 85 approach, based on training data, the SVM attempted to discover the hypersphere of a
 86 single class and assume all samples outside of this hypersphere are anomalies. Fig. 3, is
 87 demonstrated the hypersphere constructed by OCC-SVM to learn the ability to classify
 88 out-of-training distribution data based on the hypersphere.

Figure 3. Schematic of hypersphere constructed by OCC-SVM (green, red, orange points are represented healthy, faulty (anomaly) and support vector points respectively)

89 In Eq.(1), the mathematical expression of hypersphere with center c and radius r is
 90 expressed.

91

$$\min_{r,c} r^2, \quad (1)$$

subjected to:

$$\|\phi(x_i) - c\|^2 \leq r^2 \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (2)$$

where the function ϕ is the hypersphere transformation of x samples. Eq.(1) attempts to minimize the radius of the hypersphere. However, the mentioned expression is sensitive to the outlier; another flexible representation to tolerate outliers of the hypersphere is given by Eq.(3).

$$\min_{r,c,\zeta} r^2 + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^n \zeta_i, \quad (3)$$

subject to:

$$\|\phi(x_i) - c\|^2 \leq r^2 + \zeta_i, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (4)$$

OCC-SVM can be used for both kinds of anomaly detection applications, i.e., outlier detection and novelty detection.

2.3. Adaptive OCC using SVM

For the adaptation of this procedure, we measure the surface of the mentioned hypersphere by receiving the new data and save it theoretically; when data is coming from the healthy stage, this surface should be more or less at the same level; in other hands, when data is coming from the faulty area this surface dramatically increased. Therefore, changing points between regimes can be found by defining a threshold or by visual inspection.

2.4. Robust variance

What is robust variance?

3. Simulation and Results

In this section, we apply the proposed procedure to simulated data. There are two cases: deterministic trend describing the degradation process mixed with (a) Gaussian, and (b) non-Gaussian noise. The model is described as follows:

$$HI(t) = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} a & t \leq 1000 \\ b \cdot t & 1000 < t \leq 1600 \\ c \cdot \exp(d \cdot t) & t > 1600 \end{array} \right\} + \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \sigma_1 \cdot N(t) & t \leq 1000 \\ \sigma_2 \cdot t \cdot N(t) & 1000 < t \leq 1600 \\ \sigma_3 \cdot \exp(t) \cdot N(t) & t > 1600 \end{array} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where a, b, c, d are constant parameters that are related to deterministic parts, and $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are parameters responsible for the scales of noise parts. Moreover, $\{N(t)\}$ is a noise. Internal and external Gaussian noise is present in every real system due to various reasons. Unfortunately, the case becomes much more complicated when additional non-Gaussian behavior is present in the signal. Such a model of the signal is inspired by real long-term data we collected from various machines. The source of non-Gaussian noise may be related to machine design, the process related to machine operation, electromagnetic interference, etc.

3.1. α stable distribution as a model of Non-Gaussian noise

For non-Gaussian case, the symmetric α -stable distribution has been selected as an example of heavy-tailed, non-Gaussian distribution [17–21].

The α -stable distribution is defined by its characteristic function and it is characterised by four parameters: α (stability), β (skewness), σ (scale) and μ (location). How-

122 ever, for a symmetric case, it is assumed $\beta = \mu = 0$, and the corresponding characteristic
 123 function takes the form

$$E[e^{itX}] = \exp\{-\sigma^\alpha |t|^\alpha\}. \quad (6)$$

124 The α is known as the stability index and takes values in the interval $(0, 2]$. It should be
 125 noted that the α -stable distribution reduces to the Gaussian distribution when $\alpha = 2$. In
 126 case of decreasing α value, the distribution is significantly different from the Gaussian
 127 distribution [22]. In the presented simulation study, we assume the stability index is
 128 equal to 1.8.

Figure 4. Long-term data variation model used in this paper - non-Gaussian case

129 3.2. Results for simulated signal

130 In this subsection, we tried applying our proposed methodology to simulated data
 131 based on the mentioned reference.

132 3.2.1. OCC and AOCC in presence of Gaussian noise

133 In the following, the degradation curve is simulated based on Section 5, and it is
 134 shown in panel (a) in Fig. 5 in the presence of Gaussian noise. Also, the mean and
 135 variance of degradation curves are calculated and illustrated in panels (b) and (c) in Fig.
 136 5 as selected features for the input of OCC, respectively. It should be noted that the mean
 137 and variance are calculated for a window length of 20 data points without overlapping.

Figure 5. Health Index (HI) in the presence of Gaussian noise, (a) simulated degradation curves or health index (HI), (b) Variance of HI, (c) Mean of HI.

138 In Fig. 6, the results of OCC and AOCC are presented. Panel (a) is shown the
 139 health index with blue color and data used for extracting features for training OCC
 140 with red color. In conventional OCC approaches, the features extracted from the red
 141 part are employed to define the border for novelty detection. The boundary detected
 142 based on panel (a) is presented in panel (c). Also, based on the fact more data has more
 143 information, we added extra data for training see panel (b); by coming the new data,
 144 the OCC retrained again with this data, and this procedure is continued adaptively
 145 till reached the critical point that machine is going to the faulty area. By comparing
 146 panel (c) and panel (d), it can be seen the detected surface SVM-AOCC boundary is
 147 increased rather than classic SVM-OCC see panel (d) (SVM-AOCC detects solid black
 148 line, and SVM-OCC detects black dash line in panel (c) that transferred in panel (d) for
 149 comparison). This increased surface of the SVM-OCC boundary that results from the
 150 adaptive procedure has a few benefits, such as reduced blunder alarm.

Figure 6. The results of the proposed methodology in the presence of Gaussian noise. (a) Health index (HI) and the small data for the input of SVM-OCC, (b) Health index (HI) and the significant amount of data for the input of SVM-OCC, (c) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (a) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC, (d) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (b) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC and the black dash the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC based on panel (a).

151 In Fig. 7, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC in each step is demon-
 152 strated to detect the critical point. As seen in this case which the observed noise has
 153 Gaussian characteristics, the surface of the boundary detected is approximately constant
 154 till window 56; after that, the surface of the boundary detected dramatically increased,
 155 which can be a promising sign of changing the status of the machine to the faulty area.
 156 By comparing the real changing point that happened in window's number=50 with the
 157 detected point by the proposed approach in window's number=56, it can conclude that
 158 the proposed method has a delay in the detected changing point that can be the result
 159 of a slight change from the healthy area to the faulty area. Furthermore, in Fig. 7 can
 160 be seen another jump in the surface value of boundary around window's number=80
 161 related to the changing degradation regime to the critical regime.

Figure 7. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC.

162 To confirm the performance of the proposed method, we have repeated this procedure for to 50 simulated data set and the results are presented in Fig. 8 as box plot. As it
 163 can be seen based on this fact the scale of the noise is constant all results are the same.
 164

Figure 8. Box plot for 50 simulated cases in the present of Gaussian noise

165 3.2.2. OCC and AOCC in the presence of non-Gaussian noise

166 In the following, the degradation process is simulated when the observed noise
 167 includes non-Gaussian characteristics. For a non-Gaussian case, the symmetric α -stable
 168 distribution is selected as an example of heavy-tailed, non-Gaussian distribution [17–21].
 169 It is assumed the $\alpha = 1.8$.

170 Panel (a) in Fig. 9 is shown the simulated degradation curve (health index(HI))
 171 in the presence of non-Gaussian noise. Furthermore, the mean, variance, median and
 172 robust variance of degradation curves are calculated and illustrated in panels (b), (c),
 173 (d) and (e) in Fig. 9, respectively. As seen in panels (b) and panel (c), due to noise with

174 non-Gaussian characteristics in raw signal, a few spikes have appeared in features space,
 175 making a challenge for classic methods that developed based on Gaussian features.
 176 However, these spike has not any particular effect on the robust features in panels (d)
 177 and (e). It should be noted that the features are calculated for a window length of 20
 178 data points without overlapping.

Figure 9. Health Index (HI) in the presence of non-Gaussian noise with $\alpha = 1.8$, (a) HI and CP, (b) variance of HI, (c) mean of HI, (d) robust variance of HI, (e) median of HI.

179 In Fig. 10, the results of OCC and AOCC are presented. Panel (a) is shown the
 180 health index with blue color and data used for extracting features for training OCC with
 181 red color. The features extracted from the red part are used to identify the border for
 182 OCC. The boundary detected based on panel (a) is presented in panel (c). Furthermore,
 183 we added extra data for training see panel (b); by coming up with the new data, the
 184 OCC retrained again with this data, and this procedure is continued adaptively till it
 185 reached the critical point at which the machine went to the faulty area. By comparing
 186 panel (c) and panel (d), it can be seen that the detected surface SVM-AOCC boundary is
 187 increased rather than classic SVM-OCC see panel (d) (SVM-AOCC detects solid black
 188 line, and SVM-OCC detects black dash line in panel (c) that transferred in panel (d)
 189 for comparison). As discussed, this increased surface of the SVM-OCC boundary that
 190 results from the adaptive procedure can help to reduce blunder alarms.

Figure 10. The results of the proposed methodology in the presence of non-Gaussian noise. (a) Health index (HI) and the small data for the input of SVM-OCC, (b) Health index (HI) and the significant amount of data for the input of SVM-OCC, (c) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (a) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC, (d) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (b) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC and the black dash the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC based on panel(a).

191 In Fig.11, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC in each step is demon-
 192 strated to detect the critical point. As seen in this case where the observed noise has
 193 non-Gaussian characteristics, the surface of the boundary detected is fluctuated and has
 194 no clear trend like the case with Gaussian noise Fig. 11. This kind of trend can cause
 195 problems for the application that uses OCC methods for fault detection; for instance, if it
 196 uses eight windows for training, the OCC defines a boundary with a high surface that
 197 can cause the overestimated faulty area. However, it can be seen that after window's
 198 number=58, the surface of the boundary detected is dramatically increased and not
 199 reduced again, and it can be concluded that this is a promising sign of changing the
 200 machine's status to the faulty area. By comparing the real changing point that happened
 201 in window's number=50 with the detected point by the proposed approach in win-
 202 dow's number=58, it can conclude that the proposed method has a delay in the detected
 203 changing point. Furthermore, in Fig.11 can be seen another jump in the surface value of
 204 boundary around window's number=80 related to the changing degradation regime to
 205 the critical regime.

Figure 11. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC in the presence of non-Gaussian noise.

206 In Fig.12, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC, which used robust
 207 features (median and robust variance) for training in each step, is demonstrated
 208 to detect the critical point. As seen in this case where the observed noise has non-Gaussian
 209 characteristics, the surface of the boundary detected is approximately constant till
 210 window 56; after that, the surface of the boundary detected increased, which can be a
 211 promising sign of changing the status of the machine to the faulty area. By comparing
 212 the real changing point that happened in window's number=50 with the detected point
 213 by the proposed approach in window's number=56, it can conclude that the proposed
 214 method has a delay in the detected changing point that can be the result of a slight change
 215 from the healthy area to the faulty area. However, it could handle the non-Gaussian
 216 effect of the signal.

Figure 12. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC in the presence of non-Gaussian noise by using robust features (Median and robust variance).

217 To confirm the performance of the proposed method, we have repeated this proce-
 218 dure for 50 simulated data sets by using robust features and the results are presented in
 219 Fig. 13 as a box plot. As it can be seen based on this fact, the scale of the noise is constant,
 220 all results are the same.

Figure 13. Box plot for 50 simulated cases in the presence of non-Gaussian noise by using robust features (median and robust variance)

221 4. Actual case and Results

222 This section presents the results of applying the proposed procedure to real data
 223 sets. Again, two data sets are considered. The first data set that we used is the FEMTO
 224 data set, which is known as one of the benchmark data sets. Also, It could be considered
 225 a case with Gaussian noise. The second data set is wind turbine bearings data. It can be
 226 considered as a case containing non-Gaussian.

227 4.1. FEMTO data set

228 The FEMTO data set [23] was acquired by Franche-Comté Electronics Mechanics
 229 Thermal Science and Optics–Sciences and Technologies institute from a PRONOSTIA
 230 platform. The test rig is presented in Fig. 14. The data set was shared during the
 231 prognosis challenge at the conference IEEE PHM 2012. The data set contains 17 historical
 232 long-term feature sets describing the degradation of bearing. Two accelerometers and a
 233 temperature sensor were used to acquire acceleration and temperature. The speed of
 234 the shaft was kept stable during the test. It is assumed that the failure of the bearing
 235 occurs when the amplitude of the vibration signal has arrived above 20 g. This data
 236 set was used in many publication for segmentation [24–28], construction of the health
 237 index [29–36] and predicting RUL [37–42].

Figure 14. PRONOSTIA test Bench. [23]

238 4.2. Wind turbine

239 The wind turbine data set is one of the well-known data set used regularly for
 240 prognosis area [43–46]. This data set can be considered a real case with non-Gaussian
 241 characteristics. More information about the wind turbine data set, see Fig. 15, can be
 242 found in these references [43,46].

Figure 15. Test Bench of the wind turbine [46].

243 4.3. Results for FEMTO

244 In this subsection, we applied the proposed method to one of the FEMTO data set
 245 case studies. In this paper, bearing 1 1 is set as a case study. The root means square
 246 (RMS) of each vibration set is used as the health index (HI); see panel (a) in Fig. 16.
 247 Likewise, the mean and variance of HI are calculated and shown in panels (b) and (c) in
 248 Fig. 16 as selected features for the input of OCC, respectively. It should be noted that
 249 the mean and variance are calculated for a window length of 20 data points without
 250 overlapping.

Figure 16. Health Index(HI) and features for FEMTO data set, (a) Health index(HI) and CP, (b) variance of HI, (c) mean of HI.

251 In Fig. 17, the results of OCC and AOCC are presented. Panel (a) is shown the
 252 health index with blue color and data used for extracting features for training OCC with
 253 red color. In conventional OCC approaches, the features extracted from the red part are
 254 employed to define the border for OCC. The boundary detected based on panel (a) is
 255 presented in panel (c). Also, we added extra data for training see panel (b); by coming
 256 up with the new data, the OCC retrained again with this data, and this procedure is
 257 continued adaptively till it reached the critical point that the machine is going to the
 258 faulty area. By comparing panel (c), and panel (d), it can be seen that the detected
 259 surface SVM-AOCC boundary is increased rather than classic SVM-OCC see panel (d)
 260 (SVM-AOCC detects solid black line, and SVM-OCC detects black dash line in panel (c)
 261 that transferred in panel (d) for comparison).

Figure 17. The results of the proposed methodology for the FEMTO data set. (a) Health index (HI) and the small data for the input of SVM-OCC, (b) Health index (HI) and the significant amount of data for the input of SVM-OCC, (c) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (a) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC, (d) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (b) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC and the black dash the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC based on panel(a).

262 In Fig. 18, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC in each step is demon-
 263 strated to detect the critical point. As seen in this case, the surface of the boundary
 264 detected is approximately constant till window 71; after that, the surface of the boundary
 265 detected smoothly increased till the window's number=79; after the window's num-
 266 ber=79 can be seen a dramatically increased in the value of the surface area, which can a
 267 promising sign of changing the status of the machine to the faulty area. By comparing
 268 the detected point by the proposed approach in window's number=72 with other paper
 269 [26], it can conclude that the proposed method has detected changing point properly.
 270 Furthermore, in Fig. 18 can be seen another jump in the surface value of the boundary
 271 around the window's number=138 related to the changing degradation regime to the
 272 critical regime.

Figure 18. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC for FEMTO data set.

273 In Fig. 19, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC, which used robust
 274 features (median and robust variance) in each step, is demonstrated to detect the critical
 275 point. As seen in this case, the surface of the boundary detected is approximately
 276 constant till window 72; after that, the surface of the boundary detected smoothly
 277 increased till the window's number=79; after the window's number=79 can be seen, a
 278 dramatically increased in the value of the surface area, which can a promising sign of
 279 changing the status of the machine to the faulty area. By comparing the detected point by
 280 the proposed approach in window's number=72 with other papers [26], it can conclude
 281 that the proposed method has detected changing point properly. Furthermore, in Fig.
 282 19, another jump in the surface value of boundary around the window's number=138
 283 related to the changing degradation regime to the critical regime can be seen. Also, it
 284 can be seen the results of using robust features (median and mean) more or less are the
 285 same as the results of employing non-robust features (mean and variance) for this case
 286 study on the FEMTO data set.

Figure 19. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC for FEMTO data set by using robust features (median and robust variance).

287 *4.4. Results for wind turbine*

288 In this subsection, we applied the proposed method to one of the wind turbine
 289 data set case studies. In this paper, the bearing is set as a case study. The RMS of each
 290 vibration set is used as the health index (HI); see panel (a) in Fig. 20. Likewise, the mean,
 291 variance, robust variance and median of HI are calculated and shown in panels (b), (c),
 292 (d), and (e) in Fig. 20, respectively. It should be noted that the mean and variance are
 293 calculated for a window length of 20 data points without overlapping.

Figure 20. Health Index (HI) and features for wind turbine data set, (a) health index (HI) and CP, (b) variance of HI, (c) mean of HI, (d) robust variance of HI, (e) median of HI.

294 In Fig. 21, the results of OCC and AOCC are presented. Panel (a) is shown the
 295 health index with blue color and data used for extracting features for training OCC with
 296 red color. In conventional OCC approaches, the features extracted from the red part are
 297 employed to define the border for OCC. The boundary detected based on panel (a) is
 298 presented in panel (c). Also, we added extra data for training see panel (b); by coming
 299 up with the new data, the OCC retrained again with this data, and this procedure is
 300 continued adaptively till it reached the critical point that the machine is going to the
 301 faulty area. By comparing panel (c) and panel (d), it can be seen that the detected
 302 surface SVM-AOCC boundary is increased rather than classic SVM-OCC see panel (d)
 303 (SVM-AOCC detects solid black line, and SVM-OCC detects black dash line in panel (c)
 304 that transferred in panel (d) for comparison). This increased surface of the SVM-OCC
 305 boundary that results from the adaptive procedure has a few benefits, such as reduced
 306 blunder alarm.

Figure 21. The results of the proposed methodology for wind turbine data set. (a) Health index (HI) and the small data for the input of SVM-OCC, (b) Health index (HI) and the significant amount of data for the input of SVM-OCC, (c) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (a) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC, (d) the results of SVM-OCC based on the panel (b) red plus sign are data that used for training the blue circles are the rest of data, and the big black circle is the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC and the black dash the hypersphere detected by SVM-OCC based on panel (a).

307 In Fig. 22, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC in each step is demon-
 308 strated to detect the critical point. As seen in this case, the surface of the boundary
 309 detected is approximately constant till window number 107; after that, the value of the
 310 surface area is dramatically increased, which can be a promising sign of changing the
 311 status of the machine to the faulty area. By comparing the detected point by the pro-
 312 posed approach in [Compare with which paper?](#) RZ: [Any reference is needed](#) window's
 313 number=100 with other papers, it can conclude that the proposed method has a delay in
 314 the detected changing point that can be the result of a slight change from the healthy
 315 area to the faulty area.

Figure 22. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC for wind data set

316 In Fig. 23, the surface of the boundary detected by SVM-OCC, which used robust
 317 features (median and robust variance) in each step, is demonstrated to detect the critical
 318 point. As seen in this case, the surface of the boundary detected is approximately
 319 constant till window 108; after that, the surface area value is dramatically increased,
 320 which can be a promising sign of changing the status of the machine to the faulty area. By
 321 comparing the detected point by the proposed approach in *Compare with which paper?*
 322 window's number=117 with other papers, it can conclude that the proposed method
 323 has a delay in the detected changing point that can result from a slight change from
 324 the healthy area to the faulty area. Like, the previous results of using robust
 325 features (median and mean) more or less are the same as the results of employing non-robust
 326 features (mean and variance) for this case study on the wind turbine data set.

Figure 23. Changing the surface of boundary detected by SVM-OCC for wind turbine data set by using robust features (median and robust variance)

327 5. Discussion

328 From the simulation data sets section, we demonstrated the effect of the non-
 329 Gaussian noise on the performance of SVM-OCC when it uses a classical and robust
 330 statistic. Based on the results of Section 3.2, we saw that when we have noise with non-
 331 Gaussian characteristics, using classical statistics such as mean and variance sensitive to
 332 outliers for training the SVM-OCC led us to misestimate the border of SVM-OCC, which
 333 is made early or late alarm for the condition monitoring system. In contrast, we have
 334 illustrated that this problem does not happen if robust statistics such as median and
 335 robust variance are employed to train SVM-OCC, and we can get more reliable results.
 336 By looking at the results performed for the FEMTO data set by using the classical statistic
 337 (mean and variance) and robust statistics (median and robust variance) can be concluded
 338 the results are close together, which come from the fact the noise observed from FEMTO
 339 data set is more relative to the noise with Gaussian characteristics. This fact is proved in
 340 our last paper [15]. Also, by comparing the results with the actual changing point from
 341 this data set in literature [26], we can see that both methods detected this point properly.
 342 It should be noted that we are aware that OCC is always worse than supervised training.
 343 Furthermore, the results performed for wind turbines using classical and robust statistics
 344 are closer together. Nevertheless, in our previous study, we proved the observed noise is
 345 closer to the non-Gaussian noise but not so far from Gaussian noise [15]. The comparison
 346 results are presented in the table.1

Table 1: Comparison the real data sets results

Data set	detected CP with classical statistic	detected CP with robust statistic	reference
FEMTO	1420-1440	1440-1460	1429 [26]
Wind turbine	2140-20160	2140-20160	

347 6. Conclusions

348 The paper proposes introducing an adaptive technique for long-term diagnosis
349 based on one class classification (OCC) and also clarifies the effect of noise with non-
350 Gaussian characteristics on OCC application. One of the challenging subjects in the
351 OCC application is selecting enough data for the training data; if we do not use enough
352 of amount data that will not be updated, the model will not be trained properly, so it
353 may cause an early and false alarm. Unfortunately, initially, we have to assume a small
354 portion of data for training to be sure that will be a data set related to good condition.
355 Also, because most of the machines are working in harsh areas such as mining, we can be
356 seen noise with non-Gaussian characteristics, which can make challenges for traditional
357 classic approaches that assume the noise has Gaussian distribution; we have tried to
358 clarify the effect on the performance of the OCC application. To do this work based
359 on reference [15], it assumed the degradation model follows 3 stage regime (Healthy,
360 degradation, and critical regime), and it has simulated the case with Gaussian and non-
361 Gaussian noise. Also, we propose the statistical parameterization of the data performed
362 locally, i.e., using short moving windows (the mean and variance are selected as input of
363 OCC), and then SVM-OCC and the proposed adaptive SVM-OCC technique are applied.
364 It can be seen in the case of Gaussian noise when we used the adaptive version, which
365 means we used a large amount of data with training SVM-OCC; the surface of the
366 hypersphere detected as the border of healthy and faulty was increased that it can help
367 to a reduced early alarm. However, the situation in the case of non-Gaussian noise is
368 entirely different; for SVM-OCC ultimately depends on whether the is data selected for
369 training includes the outlier or not; if yes, it can make underestimate the fault, and for
370 the adaptive SVM-OCC, the surface of hypersphere detected as the border of healthy
371 and faulty has fluctuated during the procedure; its difficult to estimate the changing
372 point correctly that can be coming to this fact, in the case of non-Gaussian noise, the
373 idea of moving windows needs to be revised because one outlier will deliver several
374 features with bias. Also, simple statistics that represent data with Gaussian noise are
375 not optimal for non-Gaussian data. For instance, some features like mean and variance
376 are sensitive to the outlier; in addition, for such a heavy-tailed process, the variance is
377 not defined. This means, we need to use robust features like median instead of mean
378 and robust variance instead of classical one which can handle the effect of non-Gaussian
379 noise. Finally, we applied the proposed method to two real datasets named FEMTO and
380 wind turbine to evaluate the method's performance. Because the observed noise of these
381 two data sets is close to the Gaussian, the result of using robust features (median and
382 robust variance) and non-robust features are more or less the same and could detect the
383 changing points by acceptable error.

384 Author Contributions:

385 Data Availability Statement

386 Archived data sets cannot be accessed publicly according to the NDA agreement
387 signed by the authors.

388 Acknowledgments

389 The authors (Hamid Shiri) gratefully acknowledge the European Commission for
390 its support of the Marie Skłodowska Curie program through the ETN MOIRA project
391 (GA 955681).

392 Project no. POIR.01.01.01-00-0350/21 entitled "A universal diagnostic and prognostic
393 module for condition monitoring systems of complex mechanical structures operating
394 in the presence of non-Gaussian disturbances and variable operating conditions" co-
395 financed by the European Union from the European Regional Development Fund under
396 the Intelligent Development Program. The project is carried out as part of the competition
397 of the National Center for Research and Development no: 1/1.1.1/2021 (Szybka Ścieżka)

398 -Forough Moosavi, Agnieszka Wylomanska, and Radoslaw Zimroz.
399 Jacek Wodecki Supported by the Foundation for Polish Science (FNP).

400 **Conflicts of interest**

401 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

402

- 403 1. Bartkowiak, A.; Zimroz, R. Outliers analysis and one class classification approach for
404 planetary gearbox diagnosis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. IOP Publishing, 2011,
405 Vol. 305, p. 012031.
- 406 2. Janssens, J.H.; Flesch, I.; Postma, E.O. Outlier detection with one-class classifiers from ML
407 and KDD. 2009 International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications. IEEE, 2009,
408 pp. 147–153.
- 409 3. Li, H.; Qiu, H.; Sun, S.; Chang, J.; Tu, W. Credit scoring by one-class classification driven
410 dynamical ensemble learning. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* **2022**, *73*, 181–190.
- 411 4. Dreiseitl, S.; Osl, M.; Scheibböck, C.; Binder, M. Outlier detection with one-class SVMs: an
412 application to melanoma prognosis. *AMIA annual symposium proceedings*. American
413 Medical Informatics Association, 2010, Vol. 2010, p. 172.
- 414 5. Sabokrou, M.; Khalooei, M.; Fathy, M.; Adeli, E. Adversarially learned one-class classifier
415 for novelty detection. *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern
416 recognition*, 2018, pp. 3379–3388.
- 417 6. Oosterlinck, D.; Benoit, D.F.; Baecke, P. From one-class to two-class classification by incor-
418 porating expert knowledge: Novelty detection in human behaviour. *European Journal of
419 Operational Research* **2020**, *282*, 1011–1024.
- 420 7. Pimentel, M.A.; Clifton, D.A.; Clifton, L.; Tarassenko, L. A review of novelty detection. *Signal
421 processing* **2014**, *99*, 215–249.
- 422 8. Perera, P.; Nallapati, R.; Xiang, B. Ocgan: One-class novelty detection using gans with
423 constrained latent representations. *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer
424 Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2019, pp. 2898–2906.
- 425 9. La Grassa, R.; Gallo, I.; Landro, N. OCmst: One-class novelty detection using convolutional
426 neural network and minimum spanning trees. *Pattern Recognition Letters* **2022**, *155*, 114–120.
- 427 10. Wang, X.; Li, L.; Tian, W.; Du, Y.; Hou, R.; Xia, Y. Unsupervised one-class classification for
428 condition assessment of bridge cables using Bayesian factor analysis. *Smart Structures and
429 Systems* **2022**, *29*, 41–51.
- 430 11. Seliya, N.; Abdollah Zadeh, A.; Khoshgoftaar, T.M. A literature review on one-class classifi-
431 cation and its potential applications in big data. *Journal of Big Data* **2021**, *8*, 1–31.
- 432 12. Bishop, C.M.; others. *Neural networks for pattern recognition*; Oxford university press, 1995.
- 433 13. Japkowicz, N.; Myers, C.; Gluck, M.; others. A novelty detection approach to classification.
434 *IJCAI. Citeseer*, 1995, Vol. 1, pp. 518–523.
- 435 14. Jiang, M.F.; Tseng, S.S.; Su, C.M. Two-phase clustering process for outliers detection. *Pattern
436 recognition letters* **2001**, *22*, 691–700.
- 437 15. Framework for stochastic modelling of long-term non-homogeneous data with non-Gaussian
438 characteristics for machine condition prognosis. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*
439 **2023**, *184*, 109677.
- 440 16. Moosavi, F.; Shiri, H.; Wodecki, J.; Wyłomańska, A.; Zimroz, R. Application of Machine
441 Learning Tools for Long-Term Diagnostic Feature Data Segmentation. *Applied Sciences* **2022**,
442 *12*, 6766.
- 443 17. Grzesiek, A.; Gasiór, K.; Wyłomańska, A.; Zimroz, R. Divergence-based segmentation
444 algorithm for heavy-tailed acoustic signals with time-varying characteristics. *Sensors* **2021**,
445 *21*.
- 446 18. Hebda-Sobkiewicz, J.; Zimroz, R.; Wyłomańska, A.; Antoni, J. Infogram performance analysis
447 and its enhancement for bearings diagnostics in presence of non-Gaussian noise. *Mechanical
448 Systems and Signal Processing* **2022**, *170*, 108764.
- 449 19. Wodecki, J.; Michalak, A.; Wyłomańska, A.; Zimroz, R. Influence of non-Gaussian noise on
450 the effectiveness of cyclostationary analysis—Simulations and real data analysis. *Measurement*
451 **2021**, *171*, 108814.
- 452 20. Kruczek, P.; Zimroz, R.; Antoni, J.; Wyłomańska, A. Generalized spectral coherence for
453 cyclostationary signals with α -stable distribution. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*
454 **2021**, *159*, 107737.

- 455 21. Khinchine, A.Y.; Lévy, P. Sur les lois stables. *CR Acad. Sci. Paris* **1936**, *202*, 374–376.
- 456 22. Burnecki, K.; Wylomańska, A.; Beletskii, A.; Gonchar, V.; Chechkin, A. Recognition of stable
457 distribution with Lévy index α close to 2. *Physical Review E* **2012**, *85*, 056711.
- 458 23. Nectoux, P.; Gouriveau, R.; Medjaher, K.; Ramasso, E.; Chebel-Morello, B.; Zerhouni, N.;
459 Varnier, C. PRONOSTIA: An experimental platform for bearings accelerated degradation
460 tests. IEEE International Conference on Prognostics and Health Management, PHM'12. IEEE
461 Catalog Number: CPF12PHM-CDR, 2012, pp. 1–8.
- 462 24. Liu, Z.; Zuo, M.J.; Qin, Y. Remaining useful life prediction of rolling element bearings based
463 on health state assessment. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal
464 of Mechanical Engineering Science* **2016**, *230*, 314–330.
- 465 25. Kimotho, J.K.; Sondermann-Wölke, C.; Meyer, T.; Sextro, W. Machinery Prognostic Method
466 Based on Multi-Class Support Vector Machines and Hybrid Differential Evolution–Particle
467 Swarm Optimization. *Chemical Engineering Transactions* **2013**, *33*.
- 468 26. Zurita, D.; Carino, J.A.; Delgado, M.; Ortega, J.A. Distributed neuro-fuzzy feature forecasting
469 approach for condition monitoring. Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE Emerging Technology and
470 Factory Automation (ETFA). IEEE, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- 471 27. Guo, L.; Gao, H.; Huang, H.; He, X.; Li, S. Multifeatures fusion and nonlinear dimension
472 reduction for intelligent bearing condition monitoring. *Shock and Vibration* **2016**, *2016*.
- 473 28. Jin, X.; Sun, Y.; Que, Z.; Wang, Y.; Chow, T.W. Anomaly detection and fault prognosis for
474 bearings. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* **2016**, *65*, 2046–2054.
- 475 29. Mosallam, A.; Medjaher, K.; Zerhouni, N. Time series trending for condition assessment and
476 prognostics. *Journal of manufacturing technology management* **2014**.
- 477 30. Loutas, T.H.; Roulias, D.; Georgoulas, G. Remaining useful life estimation in rolling bear-
478 ings utilizing data-driven probabilistic e-support vectors regression. *IEEE Transactions on
479 Reliability* **2013**, *62*, 821–832.
- 480 31. Javed, K.; Gouriveau, R.; Zerhouni, N.; Nectoux, P. Enabling health monitoring approach
481 based on vibration data for accurate prognostics. *IEEE Transactions on industrial electronics*
482 **2014**, *62*, 647–656.
- 483 32. Singleton, R.K.; Strangas, E.G.; Aviyente, S. Extended Kalman filtering for remaining-useful-
484 life estimation of bearings. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* **2014**, *62*, 1781–1790.
- 485 33. Zhang, B.; Zhang, L.; Xu, J. Degradation feature selection for remaining useful life prediction
486 of rolling element bearings. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* **2016**, *32*, 547–554.
- 487 34. Hong, S.; Zhou, Z.; Zio, E.; Wang, W. An adaptive method for health trend prediction of
488 rotating bearings. *Digital Signal Processing* **2014**, *35*, 117–123.
- 489 35. Lei, Y.; Li, N.; Gontarz, S.; Lin, J.; Radkowski, S.; Dybala, J. A model-based method for
490 remaining useful life prediction of machinery. *IEEE Transactions on reliability* **2016**, *65*, 1314–
491 1326.
- 492 36. Nie, Y.; Wan, J. Estimation of remaining useful life of bearings using sparse representation
493 method. 2015 Prognostics and System Health Management Conference (PHM). IEEE, 2015,
494 pp. 1–6.
- 495 37. Li, H.; Wang, Y. Rolling bearing reliability estimation based on logistic regression model. 2013
496 International Conference on Quality, Reliability, Risk, Maintenance, and Safety Engineering
497 (QR2MSE). IEEE, 2013, pp. 1730–1733.
- 498 38. Huang, Z.; Xu, Z.; Ke, X.; Wang, W.; Sun, Y. Remaining useful life prediction for an adaptive
499 skew-Wiener process model. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* **2017**, *87*, 294–306.
- 500 39. Wang, Y.; Peng, Y.; Zi, Y.; Jin, X.; Tsui, K.L. A two-stage data-driven-based prognostic
501 approach for bearing degradation problem. *IEEE Transactions on industrial informatics* **2016**,
502 *12*, 924–932.
- 503 40. Pan, Y.; Er, M.J.; Li, X.; Yu, H.; Gouriveau, R. Machine health condition prediction via
504 online dynamic fuzzy neural networks. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* **2014**,
505 *35*, 105–113.
- 506 41. Wang, L.; Zhang, L.; Wang, X.z. Reliability estimation and remaining useful lifetime
507 prediction for bearing based on proportional hazard model. *Journal of Central South University*
508 **2015**, *22*, 4625–4633.
- 509 42. Xiao, L.; Chen, X.; Zhang, X.; Liu, M. A novel approach for bearing remaining useful life
510 estimation under neither failure nor suspension histories condition. *Journal of Intelligent
511 Manufacturing* **2017**, *28*, 1893–1914.

-
- 512 43. Saidi, L.; Ali, J.B.; Bechhoefer, E.; Benbouzid, M. Wind turbine high-speed shaft bearings
513 health prognosis through a spectral Kurtosis-derived indices and SVR. *Applied Acoustics*
514 **2017**, *120*, 1–8.
- 515 44. Saidi, L.; Bechhoefer, E.; Ali, J.B.; Benbouzid, M. Wind turbine high-speed shaft bearing
516 degradation analysis for run-to-failure testing using spectral kurtosis. 2015 16th International
517 Conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering
518 (STA). IEEE, 2015, pp. 267–272.
- 519 45. Ali, J.B.; Saidi, L.; Harrath, S.; Bechhoefer, E.; Benbouzid, M. Online automatic diagnosis of
520 wind turbine bearings progressive degradations under real experimental conditions based
521 on unsupervised machine learning. *Applied Acoustics* **2018**, *132*, 167–181.
- 522 46. Bechhoefer, E.; Schlanbusch, R. Generalized Prognostic Algorithm Implementing Kalman
523 Smoother. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* **2015**, *48*, 97–104.

